
Reimagining Financial Inclusion: India's Journey from Cash Economy to Digital Empowerment

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ABSTRACT

Financial Inclusion (FI) is a multidimensional concept that ensures equitable access to financial services such as banking, credit and insurance, particularly for the unbanked and underbanked population. In India, the shift from cash-based transactions toward digital payment systems has played a crucial role in advancing financial inclusion. Historically, about 86.6 percent of transactions in 2012 were cash-based, highlighting the need for efficient electronic payment platforms to improve liquidity flow and economic efficiency. The establishment of the National Payments Corporation of India (NPCI) has been instrumental in transforming the digital payments ecosystem. Its flagship product, the Unified Payments Interface (UPI), has revolutionized financial transactions by enabling seamless, real-time payments. UPI's growing acceptance in rural areas and its global expansion reflect its success, although challenges such as low digital

literacy, inadequate infrastructure and trust deficits persist. Telecommunication connectivity significantly influences the adoption of digital financial services. Tele-density, especially in rural areas, correlates with economic development, yet disparities remain across states. While some states like Kerala and Himachal Pradesh exhibit high rural tele-density, many regions still lag behind, limiting digital financial penetration. Disparities in financial inclusion across states can be attributed to factors such as uneven banking infrastructure, variations in digital literacy, income inequality and differences in access to internet and mobile connectivity. Southern and Western states generally perform better due to higher literacy and infrastructure development. To strengthen financial inclusion, it is essential to formalize the rural economy through improved access to institutional credit, promotion of digital literacy, expansion of Common Service Centers and effective implementation of the JAM trinity. Enhancing trust, infrastructure, and awareness will be key to achieving a more inclusive and cashless economy in India.

Introduction

Financial inclusion is defined as the availability and equality of opportunities to access financial services including banking, loan, equity and insurance products. Financial inclusion efforts typically target those who are unbanked and under banked and directs sustainable financial services to them.

Having more inclusive financial systems has been linked to stronger, sustainable economic development. Thus, achieving financial inclusion is a priority for most countries. In India also such efforts have been taken by government in different times. Committee on Financial Inclusion (CFI) was set up by the government of India under the Chairmanship of Dr. C. Rangarajan in 2006, It submitted its report in 2008. This Committee on Financial Inclusion (Rangarajan, 2008) defined Financial Inclusion as: “process of ensuring access to financial services and timely and adequate credit where needed by vulnerable groups such as weaker sections and low-income groups at affordable costs.”

On the other hand, digital transactions can be broadly defined as online or automated transactions that take place between people or organizations without the use of paper. Ex: - include swiping a debit

card at a store paying for a purchase online etc. India has initiated the revolution of digital payment system much later but much faster than other countries. Around 86.6 per cent of payments were made through cash in India in the financial year 2012.

According to the recent report of Phone pe and Boston Consulting group (BCG) in financial year 2021-22 digital payments worth \$3 trillion was processed in India. The study says in India currently 40 per cent of all transactions are done digitally. As per the World Bank's report 2017, 'India is the second largest telecommunication market. Despite 25 per cent of mobile users in India, digital literacy is merely 6 per cent of India's total mobile users' population'.

NPCI and its several products to bring financial inclusion

The birth of NPCI

In earlier days after LPG reforms, though different efforts were initiated like the Uniform Rules for Bank-to-Bank Reimbursements under Documentary credits published by the International Chamber of Commerce, Unexpired Risk Reserve (URR), Institute for Development and Research in Banking Technology (IDBRT), Indian Financial Network (INFINET), there were still no formal government oversight and regulation of payments. In 2007, the Payment and Settlement System Act came to fill several gaps in payment systems and regulation. The Act clearly outlined the rights and duties of various actors in the payments ecosystem, provided clearer legal context on topics such as dispute resolution and provided for a separate non-governmental institution to operate retail payment systems. India's leading 10 banks (6 public sector banks, 2 private banks and 2 foreign banks) were recruited by Indian Banks' Association (IBA) under RBI supervision. Each Invested US\$14 million and take a 10 per cent share in NPCI. So, Government of India held indirect control through majority share in public banks.

IDBRT's NFS/Euronet switch, that was handling most of the card transactions in the country at the time, was transferred to NPCI at book value in November 2009. NPCI officially began operation in January 2010. After NFS acquiring, NPCI began developing the Immediate Payment System (IMPS), a real time payment platform and NPCINET, which would eventually replace the INFINET network. In 2011, RBI transferred India's CTS to NPCI. Gradually it enlarged its area of operations.

Materials and method

The present study is an attempt to study the performance of financial inclusion of Rural India.

Nature and sources of data

This study is based on secondary data. Data were collected from these sources like telecommunication data from TRAI report 2021, state-wise e-transactions data from etaal.gov.in. PMJDY bank account data from pmjdy.gov.in/state-wise-statistics. Data pertaining to different demographic variables from NSO, SAS report 77th round, MOSPI, Different e-transactions data from npci.org.in. Data of financial inclusion from Financial Access Survey - IMF Data, The Global Findex Database 2021 - World Bank Group, per capita e-transactions state wise from www.statista.com/. Different schemes data from <https://dbtbharat.gov.in/reportnew/scheme-group-report>, <https://pmkisan.gov.in>. Internet penetration rate data from statista.com. State-wise ATM data from knoema.com. Reserve Bank of India Annual Report 2021-22, etc.

Analytical tools and techniques employed

The analytical techniques used to evaluate the objectives of the present study are summarized below.

Tabular presentation technique

The data from different sources has been analysed by using Excel line graph, pie chart, correlation coefficient, regression analysis, S.D, C.V etc.

1. Different electronic payment trends were shown using line graphs.
2. State-wise E-transactions per 1000 rural population of 2021 was shown through pie chart.

To make comparisons easier, the data was presented in a tabular format. The tabular presentation technique was used to examine respondents' socio-economic characteristics, such as land holding size, costs and returns in relation to the production of major fruit crops, as well as to analyse the data gathered through an opinion survey from sample farmers on the problems they face in the production and marketing of fruit crop growers.

The data were summarized with the aid of statistical tools like averages, mode, per centages etc. to compare and meaningful interpretation of results.

Results and discussion

Products umbrella

At different times NPCI have introduced different products in the market for facilitating digital transactions. The list of products which are under NPCI's control are listed below: -

RuPay, UPI, BHIM, APBS, AePS, NACH, *99#, NETC, Aadhar Pay, BBPS, IMPS, CTS, NFS, Bharat QR etc.

Here is the product journey of NPCI till 2017.

NPCI's product journey

JANUARY 2010 National Financial Switch (NFS): Provide ATM connectivity in the country and offer an e-commerce gateway.	JANUARY 2011 Aadhaar Enabled Payment System (AePS): Allows payment recipients to perform banking activities with their Aadhaar number and a biometric verification.	MARCH 2012 RuPay: NPCI's domestic debit card	FEBRUARY 2013 Aadhaar Payments Bridge System (APBS): Added capability for bulk payments and government-led social welfare programs to leverage Aadhaar.	AUGUST 2014 *99#: Allows feature phone owners to transact over NPCI rails with their bank.	APRIL 2016 Unified Payments Interface (UPI): Standardizes and secures digital financial transaction messages.	FEBRUARY 2017 Bharat QR: Common messaging standard for QR codes for merchant payments across all card schemes.
2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2016	2017
NOVEMBER 2010 Intermediate Payment System (IMPS): Provides a real-time push-payments platform, accessible over online channels including mobile.	JANUARY 2011 India's Cheque Truncation System (CTS): Transferred to NPCI.	DECEMBER 2012 National ACH (NACH): Replaced Electronic Credit System services.			DECEMBER 2016 BHIM: Supports in-app branding by any financial institution participating in UPI. National Electronic Toll Collection (NETC): Automates road toll collection.	APRIL 2017 BHIM Aadhaar: Serves as a merchant POS solution for Aadhaar payments. AUGUST 2017 Bharat BillPay System (BBPS): Licensed by RBI and focused entirely on bill payment as a service.

Source: -NPCI and the Remaking of Payments in India

All these products helped India to grow digitally. GOI is the majority stakeholder in it indirectly.

It is a company for “charitable objectives,” so profits are reinvested in it year by year. In recent years through its models, it generated billions of profits for government and as well it helped to curb the monopoly of foreign companies like VISA, Master Card through its RuPay card. Through UPI it revolutionized Indian payments system. Now India is exporting this technology to other countries. India has now surpassed many advanced countries in financial sector.

RuPay: It is the first-of-its-kind domestic card payment network of India, targeting the Indian mass population. It was launched by NPCI in March 2012. Earlier foreign card providers (VISA, Master Card) were only options left. They charged very high fees and all the profits went out of India. From the start, personal insurance was a part of RuPay. Any customer who performed at least one transaction in a three-month period with the card was covered for up to Rs 1 lakh in accident, life and permanent disability insurance.

All accounts under PMJDY were provided with RuPay cards. Over **57.86 crore bank** accounts have been opened up to **11th March 2026** as part of the **PMJDY**. In addition to the basic cards, RuPay

Classic, Platinum and Select variant cards are designed for the masses and affluent customers. It offers many benefits such as International Acceptance, free personal insurance coverage (accidental, death and permanent total disability), various merchant offers and different Cashback scheme. With time and competition rise, RuPay has developed some of new innovative products such as **RuPay Contactless** with the vision of **One Card One Nation** for all Payment systems. Later RuPay also introduced its credit card, chip/PIN facility and cards enabling e-commerce and international transactions through discover card rails.

RuPay’s success in driving financial inclusion or card adoption among the masses remains an issue of some debate. Today, activity rates for RuPay cards are relatively low, maybe due to the directive nature in which many of these cards were issued. It also makes up a small fraction of total card transactions. Over 50 lakh RuPay cards have been issued as of mid-2018 nearly 60 per cent of all those in the market is RuPay cards yet RuPay represents about 25 percent of all card transactions in year 2019 (RBI 2018 bulletin). In the year 2019-20 Rupay card usage decreased because of the COVID-19 lockdown impact (Fig 01).

Fig. 01: - Number of transactions in PoS and E-commerce portals by RuPay card holders in India in 2019-20 and 2020-21

CTS: The **Cheque truncation system** (launched in 1st Feb, 2008 and transferred to NPCI in January 2011). The technology was about replacing a physical paper cheque with an electronic image during the clearing process. Here cheque images and Magnetic Ink Character Recognition (MICR) data are captured at the collecting bank branch and transmitted electronically. Without cheque truncation, the settlement

period took several days and at high processing cost. Today all banks are mandatorily using CTS. In March 2023, 3.21 million transactions happened through CTS amounting to Rs. 67308.95 crore

Fig. 02: - Number of transactions in CTS in terms of value in India

Fig. 03: - Number of transactions in CTS in terms of volume in India

Here are two graphs showing month wise value and volume of transactions through CTS from 2016 to 2023. Both shows mostly stagnant and declining trend.

BHIM app: Its full form is Bharat Interface for Money (BHIM). It is an app that let us make simple, quick payment transactions using UPI. Smaller banks usually do not have the technical expertise to develop sophisticated banking apps. So, through this BHIM app, they can also provide online facilities to their customers. In March 2023, 23.53 million transactions happened through BHIM amounting to Rs. 7480.50 crore.

Fig. 04: - Number of transactions in BHIM app in terms of value

Fig. 05:- Number of banks services providing in BHIM app in terms of volume

But due to its public good nature it could not grow gigantically compared to other UPI service providers. In 2016, BHIM accounted for 45 per cent of all UPI transactions by volume; however, that number had reduced to 5.37 percent by March 2020. Today, Google Pay and Walmart’s Phone Pe are contending for the top place in the Indian payments app market and are trailed by Alibaba-backed Paytm. Today 486 banks are live on BHIM app.

NACH & APBs

NPCI has implemented “National Automated Clearing House (NACH)” to facilitate interbank, high volume, electronic transactions which are repetitive and periodic in nature. NACH System can be used for making bulk transactions towards distribution of subsidies, dividends, interest, salary, pension

etc. and towards collection of payments pertaining to telephone, electricity, water, loans, investments in mutual funds, insurance premium etc. Today CTS and NACH are the only two NPCI services that are mandatory for all banks to use.

NACH aim is to consolidate multiple ECS systems running across the country. NACH system also supports Financial Inclusion measures by providing support to Aadhaar based transactions. NACH’s Aadhaar Payment Bridge (APBS) System, developed by NPCI has been helping the Government in making the Direct Benefit Transfer scheme a success. APB System has been successfully channelizing the Government subsidies and benefits to the intended beneficiaries using the Aadhaar numbers.

Fig. 06: - Year-wise NACH transactions in volume

Fig. 07: - Year-wise NACH transactions in terms of value

Fig. 06 shows the no. of transaction increased over the year. Fig. 07 shows the no. of transaction increased over the year in 2017-18 decreased due to demonetization and policies and regulation made by the NPCI then increased on further years.

AePS/Aadhar Pay

AePS (Aadhaar Enabled Payment System) was launched in January 2011. It allows payment recipients to perform banking activities with their Aadhaar number and a biometric verification. Through this payment mode, a merchant would require the Aadhaar number, the name of the bank, as well as the fingerprint of the customer for formulating a cashless payment system. This would ensure that the digital transactions are validated; PIN-less as well as card-less transactions can enhance the security system as well. Furthermore, it would not require any smartphone for transactions for the customers.

According to NPCI data in March 2023 there was total 447.25 million transactions through Aadhar pay.

IMPS

Its full form is **Immediate Payment Service (IMPS)**. Till **2010**, only **NEFT & RTGS** were available to user for fund transfer and that was only during banking hours. Any such 24*7*365 real-time interbank facilities were not there. With the above context, NPCI conducted a pilot study in August and Immediate Payment Service (IMPS) was launched on 22nd November 2010.

It provides a robust and real time fund transfer which offers an instant, 24X7, interbank electronic fund transfer service. It could be accessed on multiple channels like Mobile, Internet, ATM and SMS. Currently on IMPS, 647 members are live which includes banks and PPIs (Prepaid Payment Instruments, like vouchers, Mobil wallets etc). This facility is provided by NPCI through its existing NFS switch.

Fig. 08: - Number of banks services providing in IMPS in terms of volume

Fig. 09: - Number of transactions in IMPS in terms of value

In March 2023, there were around 497.06 million transactions amounting to Rs. 546235.62 crore in a single month. Fig. 8 and 9 shows the month-wise volume and number of transactions through IMPS and banks.

*99#

It is a USSD based mobile banking service of NPCI that was initially launched in **2012**. But during its first launch it could not grab customers as only two TSPs (MTNL & BSNL) joined in initial launch. With a wider ecosystem (11 TSPs), *99# was re-launched on 28th August 2014, as part of PMJDY. Meanwhile in 2016, NPCI launched UPI. It is now available for non-internet based mobile devices in the form of dialling option (*99#) and is known as USSD 2.0. This functionality i.e., USSD 2.0 is launched along with BHIM on 30th December 2016. Key services offered under *99# service include, Sending and Receiving interbank account to account funds, balance enquiry, setting / changing UPI PIN etc. *99# service is currently offered by 83 leading banks and all GSM service providers and can be accessed in 13 different languages.

In March 2023, 0.15 million transactions happened through *99# amounting to Rs. 17.45 Crore.

Fig. 10: - Number of banks services providing in *99# in terms of value

Fig. 11: - Number of transactions in *99# in terms of volume.

Fig.10 & 11 shows the no. of transaction decreased over the years because of easy availability of other NPCI products and no. of banks providing this service is over the years stagnate.

Recent success of UPI and its analysis

UPI in a nutshell: Unified Payments interface or **UPI** was launched on 11th April 2016. It can be regarded as a miraculous revolution in modern India. In March 2023, there were about 6.86 billion transactions, amounting to 14104.43 billion Rs in a single month.

It is an Immediate money transfer through mobile device 24*7*365, single mobile application for accessing different bank accounts, single Click 2 Factor Authentication, only need mobile number or VPA, no need to enter the details such as Card no, Account number; IFSC etc. Utility Bill Payments, Over the Counter Payments, QR Code based payments can be done easily.

Fund transfer or bill payment will be completely free of cost. The biggest difference between UPI and other products, such as IMPS, is its focus on interoperability.

Google Pay, Phone pe, BHIM app, Amazon Pay, Paytm, Mobikwick all apps are UPI based platforms. These apps customize the UPI interface according to their convenience and today through their UPI adoption they have grown gigantically.

As on March, 2023 there are 339 banks live on UPI system.

Fig. 12: - Number of banks services providing in UPI in India

UPI 2.0: UPI 2.0 was released in August 2018. UPI 2.0 was released in August 2018. The new version included overdraft and the ability to pay later, among other features. Originally, UPI 2.0 was to use biometrics; however, this feature ultimately was not approved by RBI. UPI 2.0 omitted an earlier feature

whereby an Aadhaar number could be used as a payment address. UPI is now wholly separate from the Aadhaar infrastructure and related payment schemes that NPCI operates under AePS and APBS.

1. International expansion: -

UPI has seen rapid growth due to the growing ecosystem encouraged by banks and added payment service players and added cumulative adoption by the users. NPCI launched an advanced version of UPI called UPI 2.0. Improvements in August 2018 with security, ease of use for clients opens new use cases for industries and expand the UPI ecology.

The 1st global transactions initiated using the BHIM UPI was executed in Singapore on 13th Nov, 2020. After that UAE, Nepal, Bhutan also joined hands with NPCI to welcome UPI in their countries. In 2020, RBI and NPCI established NPCI International Payments Limited (NIPL) as the latter's subsidiary to expand the deployment of UPI and Rupay solutions outside India.

Fig. 15: - Year wise UPI transactions in terms of value

Fig. 16: - Year wise UPI transactions in terms of volume

Fig. 15&16 shows the year wise transaction in UPI as increased over the years both in value as well as volume.

Table 1: Shows the year wise UPI transaction over the years

Table 01: Year wise UPI transactions		
Years	Volume (Billion)	Value (in Billion Rs)
2016-17	0.018	69
2017-18	0.069	1098
2018-19	5.353	8772
2019-20	12.518	2132
2020-21	22.330	4104
2021-22	45.965	8417
2022-23	83.751	1392

In April 2022, NPCI signed a deal with Neo Pay, a payments subsidiary of UAE's Mashreq Bank. It allowed Indians in the UAE to make payments using UPI across the country. On June 16, 2022, NIPL signed MoU with France based payments solution provider Lyra network to accept UPI and RuPay cards in France. On 18 August 2022, NPCI made a partnership with Pay Xpert for acceptance of UPI in U.K (on all Pay Xpert's POS devices for in store payments and later integrate with Rupay card payments). NPCI launched 'UPI lite – On-Device wallet' to enable small-value transactions in offline mode. Similarly, it introduced the '123 Pay' UPI service to bring UPI to feature phone users.

2. Rural backlogs: -

According to a study by the Internet and Mobile Association of India (IMAI), around 16 per cent of the rural users access the internet for digital transactions, as compared to nearly 45 per cent of the urban users. In 2022, field research was done by 1Bridge, one of India's leading village commerce networks (presence in over 10000 villages), to understand the preference and usage of UPI payment patterns in rural areas. According to the survey, a mere 3-7 per cent of rural India actively uses any UPI platform to

make payments. Only 15 per cent of all transactions accounted for are online payments. 11 per cent of the digital transactions are loans or repayments between individuals.

A better trend observed in the survey was that the average transaction value for UPI payments was Rs. 1,450 which is a significant amount. The chief share of rural digital payments is for goods and services in stores, accounting for 40 per cent of all transactions. Approximately 40 per cent of rural people surveyed have absolutely no knowledge of digital payments. In rural settings, several financial institutions have not yet been set up with suitable infrastructure to support digital transactions. Thus, provision of adequate rural infrastructure to facilitate digital payments is the need of the hour. Still much more way to go for UPI penetration in rural India.

Probable reasons for FI disparity among states

1. **Bank penetration:** Many states still today are underbanked for example: -Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Assam, Arunachal Pradesh etc.
2. **Digital literacy rate:** It is a vital factor affecting digital transactions. It has been evident that Southern and western states of India have more rural digital literacy rate than other parts.
3. **ATMs per lakh population:** The ATM density in states determines how much the people use debit cards for transactions. Top states are Kerala, Goa, Delhi, Gujarat etc.
4. **Branch per 1000 population:** More bank branch means more access to financial services that leads to more e-transactions
5. **Avg. monthly income of agricultural households by states:** The more a farm family earns the more they can spend overall and digitally.
6. **Rural Tele-density (%):** The more rural people are connected with mobile and internet facility the more they can do e-transactions.

Issues and challenges in Digitalization of rural sector

1. **Low literacy rate:** According to the Survey report on 'Social Consumption: Education' during the National Sample Survey (NSS) 77th Round by the National Sample Survey Office (NSO), 22.3 per cent of rural population lack literacy, which is the greatest challenge in implementation of digitalization to rural banking.

Both Financial and Digital literacy is less. The rural population is less aware of digital world and computer/ smartphone. They even lack the basic knowledge of operating a smartphone or a computer.

2. **Inadequate infrastructure:** Smartphone penetrations, internet connectivity, electricity, banking services are not adequate. Even the biggest nationalized banks of India are finding it difficult to provide the basic banking services to the rural population. Nearly 96 per cent villages in India are electrified but only 69 per cent of homes have electricity connections, according to the World Bank report.

3. **Vulnerable system and the mistrust:** The misbelief among people is that if money has been parked in a bank, they can be cheated or refrained from withdrawing money, making them even more wary to a digital transaction. Further, the frauds that happen make the things worse.

4. **Customer resistance to new technology:** The rural people do not change so easily in the case of usage of technology, as lack of awareness on usage of digital banking services.

5. **Limited Volume and number of transactions:** Higher number and volume of transactions with the same merchant may push an individual to redirect toward ease of payment.

However, in rural areas, there are limited number and volume of transactions because of lesser demand for the goods and low level of income, people might be less willing to undertake transactions through the digital mode.

Although the **PMJDY** boosted financial inclusion, but most of the accounts made under the scheme are dormant and less or no transactions are done in them.

6. **Cost of financial services:** The cost of providing financial service is too high in rural area because of lack of infrastructural facilities and low volume of transaction in rural area.

7. **Nature of rural economy:** Most of the needs of rural people depend on cash transactions and to introduce the concept of digital payments is a very difficult task. Cash serves better than digital transaction because rural economy is mostly informal or unorganized.

8. **Poor economy:** The rural population of India is still poor and the per capita income is considerably less than the national one. This makes even the basic necessities unaffordable for the rural population.

Conclusion

Rural economy should be formalized to the extent possible. This can be done by easy availability of loans in formal sector, incentives for adopting digital economy, digitization of land records, better implementation of JAM (Jan Dhan account, Aadhar and Mobile connectivity trinity). Digital literacy is one of the biggest hurdles in transition toward cashless economy. Common Service Center (CSC) should be spread across the country, computer education in schools promoted, self-help groups (SHGs) should be trained and encouraged to spread digital literacy though trust building takes time, suitable advertisement strategies and promotion of cashless economy can help. Retailers and distributors must be encouraged to use digitization more. Government should ensure that banking personnel, telecommunication providers are working with their given mandates with other collaborations. More transparency in banking system to be achieved so that trust related issues of rural people can be resolved.

Reference

- Abraham S, 2020, Unified Payment Interface: Towards Greater Cyber Sovereignty. *ORF Issue Brief*, 2(3): 23-29.
- Anonymous, 2022, All India Report on Agriculture Census 2015-16.
- Anonymous, 2022, NSO SAS report 77th round, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation
- Anonymous, 2022, The Global Findex Database 2021 - World Bank Group,
- Anonymous, 2022, TRAI annual report 2021-22. *Telecom Regulatory Authority of India*, 1-182.
- Barik R and Sharma P, 2019, Analyzing the progress and prospects of financial inclusion in India. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 19(4): 1948.
- Dhar P and Barua N A, 2020, Financial inclusion in India- a state-wise analysis. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 11(10): 1-12.
- Gautam R S, Bhimavarapu V M and Rastogi S, 2021, Impact of Digitalization on the Farmers in India: Evidence Using Panel Data Analysis. *International Journal of Management and Humanities (IJMH)*, 6(1): 5-12.
- Nayak R, 2018, A conceptual study on digitalization of banking-issues and challenges in rural India. *Journal Homepage*, 8(6): 102-112.

- Rama Bijapurkar and Dr. Rajesh Shukla, 2020, Digital Payments Adoption in India. *NPCI-PRICE*, 4(1): 25-29.
- Ranjith P V, Kulkarni S and Varma A J, 2021, A Literature Study Of Consumer Perception Towards Digital Payment Mode In India. *Psychology and Education*, 58(1): 3304-3319.
- Ravi, Shamika. “Accelerating Financial Inclusion in India,” Brookings India Report, March 2019
- Reserve Bank of India Annual Report 2021-22,
- Satyasai K J S and Kumar A, 2020, NAFINDEX: Measure of Financial Inclusion based on NABARD All India Rural Financial Inclusion Survey (NAFIS) Data. *Special Proceedings 22nd Annual Conference of SSCA held at Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune Maharashtra*, 1(6): 117-131.
- Shobha B G, 2020, Digital Payments-Analysis of its present Status in India. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 8(7):4071-4081.
- Singh R and Malik G, 2019, Impact of digitalization on Indian rural banking customer: with reference to payment systems. *Emerging Economy Studies*, 5(1): 31-41.
- Websites referred:
- <https://dbtbharat.gov.in/reportnew/scheme-group-report>
- <https://etaal.gov.in/etaal/PopReportCensus.aspx>
- <https://pmjdy.gov.in/statewise-statistics>
- <https://pmkisan.gov.in/>
- <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/voices/unified-payments-interface-upi-usage-urban-uptake-rural-slack/?frmapp=yes>
- <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/business/india-business/upi-transaction-value-touches-rs-10-73-lakh-crore-in-aug/articleshow/93921384.cms>
- <https://www.statista.com/>
- https://agcensus.nic.in/document/agcen1516/ac_1516_report_final-220221.pdf
- <https://www.worldbank.org/en/publication/globalindex>
- <https://www.trai.gov.in/about-us/annual-reports>
- <https://rbidocs.rbi.org.in/rdocs/AnnualReport/PDFs/ORBIAR2021226AD1119FF6674A13865C988DF70B4E1A.PDF>
- <https://www.npci.org.in/what-we-do/upi/product-overview>
- <https://data.imf.org/fas>